

Master 2 MES Internship Report

Protein Characterisation of Subcellular Components Involved in the Metabolic Adaptation of Trypanosomatidae

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Formation: Master 2 - Biodiversité, Écologie et Évolution. Parcours Microbiologie | Environnement | Santé (2022-2023)

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Abstract

Trypanosomatids are a group of parasitic protozoa belonging to the Kinetoplastida class, including species from the genera *Trypanosoma* and *Leishmania*. These microorganisms possess unique organelles that play a crucial role in their nutrition and survival. An example is the glycosome, an organelle related to the peroxisome, known to contain the majority of enzymes related to the glycolytic pathway and other vital metabolic pathways. So far, the analysis of the overall glycosomal proteome in trypanosomatids has been primarily approached through conventional organelle enrichment methods. However, this approach may result in limited coverage of identified proteins. To overcome this limitation, proximity labeling methods have been extensively investigated for proteomic mapping of different subcellular compartments. Yet, their application to trypanosomatid glycosomes had not been evaluated. In our studies, we aimed to determine whether the APEX2-based proximity labeling strategy could be effectively employed for analyzing the proteomic composition of glycosomes and nucleus in *L. infantum*. To achieve this, we fused APEX2 with the glycosomal targeting signal peptide (PTS1), as well as with the nuclear localization signal (NLS). The results indicated that APEX2-PTS1 and APEX2-NLS directed specific biotinylation of the glycosome and nucleus, respectively. Our findings establish the potential feasibility of applying APEX2 in the biochemical context of *L. infantum*. As part of an ongoing effort, a comparative proteomic analysis of *L. infantum*, *T. rangeli*, and *T. brucei* is expected from our group. We believe that this approach will allow us to reveal metabolic adaptation mechanisms employed by this group of parasites, while also identifying potential pharmacological targets for the treatment of diseases associated with trypanosomatids.

Résumé

Les trypanosomatidés sont un groupe de protozoaires parasites appartenant à la classe des Kinetoplastida, comprenant des espèces des genres *Trypanosoma* et *Leishmania*. Ces microorganismes possèdent des organites uniques qui jouent un rôle crucial dans leur nutrition et leur survie. Un exemple en est le glycosome, un organite apparenté au peroxyosome, connu pour contenir la majorité des enzymes liées à la voie glycolytique et à d'autres voies métaboliques vitales. Jusqu'à présent, l'analyse du protéome global des glycosomes chez les trypanosomatidés a été principalement abordée par le biais de méthodes conventionnelles d'enrichissement des organites. Cependant, cette approche peut entraîner une couverture limitée des protéines identifiées. Pour surmonter cette limitation, les méthodes d'étiquetage de proximité ont été largement étudiées pour la cartographie protéomique de différents compartiments subcellulaires. Pourtant, leur application aux glycosomes des trypanosomatidés n'avait pas été évaluée. Dans nos études, nous avons cherché à déterminer si la stratégie de marquage de proximité basée sur APEX2 (*engineered ascorbate peroxidase*) pourrait être efficacement utilisée pour analyser la composition protéomique des glycosomes et du noyau chez *L. infantum*. Pour ce faire, nous avons fusionné APEX2 avec le peptide signal de ciblage glycosomal (PTS1), ainsi qu'avec le signal de localisation nucléaire (NLS). Les résultats ont indiqué que APEX2-PTS1 et APEX2-NLS dirigeaient spécifiquement la biotinylation du glycosome et du noyau, respectivement. Nos résultats établissent la faisabilité potentielle de l'application d'APEX2 dans le contexte biochimique de *L. infantum*. Dans la continuation de ce projet, une analyse protéomique comparative de *L. infantum*, *T. rangeli* et *T. brucei* est attendue. Nous croyons que cette approche nous permettra de déterminer les mécanismes d'adaptation métabolique employés par ce groupe de parasites, tout en identifiant également des cibles pharmacologiques potentielles pour le traitement des maladies associées aux trypanosomatidés.

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Abbreviations

APEX2: engineered modified ascorbate peroxidase

*Bgl*III: restriction enzyme

BioID: proximity-dependent Biotin-IDentification

BirA: biotin ligase enzyme

BP: biotin-phenol

EDTA: ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid

FBS: fetal bovine serum

HA: hemagglutinin tag

HRP: horseradish peroxidase

H₂O₂: hydrogen peroxide

LB: Luria-Bertani medium

NaCl: sodium chloride

NLS: nuclear localization signal

*Not*I: restriction enzyme

PCR: polymerase chain reaction

pLEXS_Y-hyg: The plasmid pLEXS_Y that contains the hyg selection marker, conferring resistance to the drug hygromycin, used for *L. infantum* transfection

pTRES-neo: The plasmid pTRES that contains the neo selection marker, conferring resistance to the drug neomycin, used for *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei* transfection.

PTS1: peroxisomal targeting signal type 1

RIPA buffer: radioimmunoprecipitation assay buffer

SDS: sodium dodecyl sulfate

SDS-PAGE: sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

SP: signal peptide

*Xba*I: restriction enzyme

*Xho*I: restriction enzyme

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I. Introduction

1. An Overview of Trypanosomatids

The Trypanosomatidae family encompasses a diverse group of parasitic protozoa belonging to the Kinetoplastids class, including species from the genera *Trypanosoma* and *Leishmania*. Some of these trypanosomatids cause severe diseases in humans, such as leishmaniasis, African trypanosomiasis, and Chagas disease. According to the World Health Organization, currently, over one billion individuals reside in endemic regions for leishmaniasis and are at risk of infection (World Health Organization, 2023). In a similar scenario, despite there being a significant drop to fewer than a thousand cases in 2018 due to intensive measures to contain the disease, during the period from 2016 to 2020, approximately 55 million individuals were at different levels of risk of contracting African trypanosomiasis (World Health Organization, 2023). Both diseases are considered lethal if left untreated. With treatment and control methods still rudimentary, the discovery of new targets for antiparasitic drugs is essential.

On the other hand, not all trypanosomatids are disease-causing agents in humans. An example of this is the parasite *T. rangeli*, which has the ability to infect triatomine bugs and mammals in the Central and South American regions (Guhl *et al.*, 2003). Despite not causing diseases in humans, this parasite is capable of inducing varying degrees of pathogenicity in its invertebrate hosts, primarily in species of the genus *Rhodnius* (Marlière *et al.*, 2022). The inclusion of *T. rangeli* in comparative studies of pathogenic trypanosomes is advantageous, as it enables discussions related to virulence, survival within host cells, and the process of pathogenesis in mammalian hosts (Grisard *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, it allows the investigation of unique aspects of parasite-vector adaptation that are specific to this trypanosome. However, there is very little information about the degree of similarity/difference between trypanosomatid species at the proteomic level.

2. The study of organelles in trypanosomatids: the glycosomes

Parasites of the Trypanosomatidae family exhibit unique eukaryotic organelles that play a crucial role in their biology and survival. For instance, glycosomes, a closely related member of peroxisomes, are organelles identified in kinetoplastids and diplomonads, known to house the majority of glycolytic enzymes, thus playing a pivotal role in the central metabolic pathway of glycolysis (Jamdhade *et al.*, 2015). The formation of peroxisomes encompasses various processes, such as protein transfer from the matrix, mobilization of lipids to shape the membranes, incorporation of proteins into the organelle's membrane, and its division (Galland *et al.*, 2010). So far, 31 proteins, designated as peroxins, have been identified as mediators of the various stages of the development of these organelles (Galland *et al.*, 2010). Two main protein import pathways into these organelles are recognized: one depends on the conserved type 1 peroxisomal targeting sequence (PTS-1), located at the carboxy-terminal end of the protein, while another involves the type 2 amino-terminal signal (PTS-2), characterized by a specific consensus sequence (Moyersoen *et al.*, 2004). It's worth noting that, despite these import pathways, some proteins can be targeted to peroxisomes without the presence of these distinctive signals.

Despite being known to house some glycolytic enzymes, the glycosomes of various trypanosomatids have been reported to contain enzymes related to other metabolic pathways:

pentose phosphate pathway, gluconeogenesis, purine salvage, β -oxidation of fatty acids, and biosynthesis of ether lipids, isoprenoids, sterols, and pyrimidines (Acosta *et al.*, 2019). Due to the presence of enzymes in pathways considered essential for the survival and nutrition of various trypanosomatids, many glycosomal enzymes have been promising targets for the development of new drugs (Barros-Alvarez *et al.*, 2014).

Another intriguing aspect is that the relatively large number of genes encoding glycosomal enzymes appears to have been acquired through one or several horizontal gene transfer events (Opperdoes *et al.*, 2006). Several protein sequences from *L. major* have shown a clear bacterial affiliation, and several sugar kinases from *L. major* are absent in other trypanosomatids. This suggests that both the acquisition of new genes and the loss of existing genes have occurred in *Trypanosoma* and *Leishmania* lineages, and these events may have been fundamental for the formation of new trypanosomatid species.

In this context, a comprehensive comparative analysis that effectively identifies the proteins present in glycosomes in the genera *Leishmania* and *Trypanosoma* would broaden our understanding of the highly relevant function played by this organelle in parasite metabolism. In addition to contributing to a better understanding of how these species adapt metabolically over evolution, this analysis could also potentially lead to the discovery of promising targets for the development of drug therapies.

3. Proximity labelling assays: APEX2

As observed, trypanosomatids possess distinct organelles with significant relevance to their biology. To comprehend the composition of these organelles, subproteomic analysis emerges as a crucial strategy. Traditionally, the workflow of cellular compartment proteomic analysis involves prior enrichment of the target compartment, followed by protein identification through mass spectrometry techniques. However, these approaches are constrained by currently available purification methods, as obtaining highly pure intact organelles is often impractical (Vélez-Ramírez *et al.*, 2021). To overcome this limitation in subproteomic studies, several proximity-dependent labeling methods have been developed. Generally, proximity labeling relies on enzymes that convert a substrate into a reactive radical that covalently marks neighbouring proteins. The short half-life of the product generated by these enzymes ensures that only proteins in the vicinity of the enzyme are covalently modified, enabling labeling within a specific compartment. The generation of a reactive biotin derivative is the central principle of the two most commonly used labeling methods today: BioID and APEX.

The BioID approach utilizes a mutant form of the biotin ligase enzyme BirA from *Escherichia coli* (BirA*) (Roux *et al.*, 2012). In the presence of ATP and biotin, BirA* biotinylates proteins by catalyzing the conversion of biotin into a reactive radical, biotinyl-5'-AMP, which specifically labels exposed primary amines of lysine residues (Choi-Rhee *et al.*, 2004). Cells expressing BirA* are subjected to incubation with biotin over a few hours. Subsequently, biotinylated proteins are captured by a streptavidin affinity matrix for identification through mass spectrometry. The mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of generated peptides and their fragment ions are used to identify peptide sequences through computational comparison with a specific database.

Similarly, APEX is an ascorbate peroxidase that catalyzes the oxidation of biotin-phenol to the short-lived biotin-phenoxy radical (<1 ms) in the presence of H_2O_2 and biotin (Martell *et al.*, 2015). This generated phenolic radical can covalently bind to electron-rich amino acids in nearby endogenous proteins (Figure 1). An improved version of APEX, called APEX2, has additional mutations that enhance labeling activity and sensitivity, as well as improve stability

of APEX2-labeled proteins (Lam *et al.*, 2015; Huang *et al.*, 2019). Cells expressing APEX are incubated with biotin-phenol, followed by exposure to H₂O₂ for 1 minute to induce biotinylation. The main advantage of APEX over BioID is its significantly faster labeling kinetics (minutes vs. hours). This allows for greater precision in protein identification, as lower biotin diffusion rates can lead to less cross-labeling of distant proteins. Additionally, this faster labeling rate enables capturing transient or short-lived protein interactions, which is especially useful for investigating dynamic interactions or rapid events within cells (Trinkle-Mulcahy *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, APEX provides a more precise and dynamic approach for investigating subcellular-level protein interactions.

Figure 1. Scheme showing APEX2-catalyzed biotinylation. This example shows APEX (yellow Pac-Man) targeted at some subcellular region of interest.

To achieve spatially restricted labeling, both the BioID and APEX approaches involve fusing the gene sequences of the enzymes with target signal peptide sequences, a protein of interest, or an antibody.

4. The proteome of Trypanosomatid glycosomes

The proteome of trypanosomatid glycosomes has been investigated through the isolation and purification of these organelles using various methodologies. So far, proximity-dependent labeling methods have not been reported for the glycosomes of these parasites. The proteome of *T. cruzi* glycosomes was recently determined for purified organelles from epimastigotes using the conventional organelle enrichment methodology (Acosta *et al.*, 2019). In addition to glycolysis, it has been reported that enzymes involved in other metabolic processes are present in glycosomes, such as fatty acid β -oxidation, purine salvage, pentose-phosphate pathway, gluconeogenesis, and the biosynthesis of ether lipids, isoprenoids, sterols, and pyrimidines (Acosta *et al.*, 2019). By employing epitope tagging and magnetic bead enrichment techniques, the proteome of glycosomes in the procyclic forms of *T. brucei* was similarly investigated (Güther *et al.*, 2014). The authors of this study confirmed the presence of several pathways previously mentioned and suggested within this organelle. They also identified previously unanticipated proteins, such as phosphatases (Güther *et al.*, 2014). In order to gain a deeper understanding of the biological processes in the parasite *L. donovani*,

techniques involving differential ultracentrifugation and density gradient were employed to achieve subcellular fractionation of the promastigote stage (Jardim *et al.*, 2018).

Despite numerous research efforts, many questions regarding the multiple properties and biological functions of glycosomes still remain. A comparative study of the proteomes of this organelle across different trypanosomatids could be intriguing to facilitate an in-depth discussion about potential metabolic adaptations within this group.

5. Objectives

In order to enhance the investigation of the subproteome of unique organelles in trypanosomatids, numerous studies have been previously conducted (Jamdhade *et al.*, 2015; Galland *et al.*, 2010; Acosta *et al.*, 2019). As explained earlier, the utilization of the APEX2 methodology offers a precise and dynamic approach for studying organelle proteins. However, this methodology has not yet been applied to the glycosomes of any trypanosomatid. Therefore, the initial objective of this study was to test and validate the APEX2 methodology across different trypanosomatids as living *L. infantum*, *T. rangeli*, and *T. brucei* with the aim of mapping the proteome of the glycosome and nucleus to facilitate an in-depth discussion about potential metabolic adaptations within trypanosomatids.

To achieve this, we planned:

Generate transfectants expressing the APEX2 protein with nuclear localization signal (NLS) or peroxisomal targeting signal type 1 (PTS1) through molecular cloning of gene inserts with the expression vector pLEXSY-hyg for *L. infantum* or pTREX-neo for *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei*. Additionally, a control would be included to verify the targeting of the proteins to the desired organelles by fusing the fluorescent mNeonGreen gene with the signal peptide sequence.

- 1- Produce transfectants expressing mNeonGreen protein by cloning the fused gene sequence with the signal peptide into the pLEXSY-hyg or pTREX-neo expression plasmids.
- 2- Assess protein expression by Western blot and immunofluorescence analyses in the transfected clones, as the APEX2 and mNeonGreen genes both fused to the hemagglutinin (HA) tag, through labeling with the α -HA antibody.
- 3- Perform the APEX2-based proximity biotinylation assay in living cells.
- 4- Confirm through Western blot and immunofluorescence the APEX2-based biotinylation assay, using high-affinity streptavidin for biotin labeled molecules in order to carry out in future the biotinylated protein identification by proteomics.

Figure 2 shows the flowchart of the set of experiments that have been conducted and others that are yet to be performed for *L. infantum*. The same process will be carried out for *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei* after their transfection at the Laboratory of Biochemistry and Protein Chemistry at the University of Brasília, Brazil.

Figure 2. Summary of the set of experiments planned in the project. mNeonGreen gene or APEX2 gene fused to the hemagglutinin (HA) tag and nuclear localization signal (NLS) or peroxisomal targeting signal type 1 (PTS1) sequences into the pLEXSy-hyg expression plasmid.

II. Material and methods

1. Cell Culture

Promastigote forms of wild-type *L. infantum* were cultured in Schneider's insect medium (Sigma Aldrich) supplemented with 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of gentamicin, penicillin, and 20% (v/v) heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) at 27 °C. Parasites transfected with cassettes containing the HygR gene (conferring resistance to hygromycin) were cultured in the aforementioned medium with the addition of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of hygromycin B (Sigma Aldrich). Passage of cultures was performed every two days to maintain the clones.

2. Construction of episomal expression plasmids

The construction of inserts was carried out based on the fusion of signal peptides (SPs) with the gene sequence of APEX2 or mNeonGreen. The signal peptides were used to target the proteins to two specific organelles: the nucleus (NLS) and glycosome (PTS1). The SPs were fused downstream of the APEX2 or mNeonGreen gene sequence. For each construct, a 3 x HA tag was also added to the N-terminal region, before the SP, to facilitate confirmation of protein expression by the parasite in the respective organelle through Western blotting and immunofluorescence. The inserts were synthesized (Genone) and cloned into commercial vectors pUC57, flanked by *Bgl*III and *Not*I restriction sites.

For the sub-cloning procedure, the restriction enzymes *Bgl*III (New England Biolabs Inc.) and *Not*I (New England Biolabs Inc.) were used following the manufacturer's instructions. After digestion of the pUC57 vectors, the inserts were analyzed on a 1% agarose gel, with manual excision of the bands containing the inserts. After excision, the gel bands containing the inserts were extracted using the MinElute Gel Extraction Kit (QIAGEN).

In order to obtain the constructs APEX2-HA-PTS1-pLEXSY-hyg2, APEX2-HA-NLS-pLEXSY-hyg2, mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1-pLEXSY-hyg2, and mNeonGreen-HA-NLS-pLEXSY-hyg2, the pLEXSY-hyg2 plasmid (Jena Bioscience) (Figure 3) containing its stuffer sequence was previously digested with the *Bgl*III and *Not*I restriction enzymes. The digested plasmids were excised from a 1% (w/v) agarose gel and purified using the MinElute Gel Extraction Kit (QIAGEN) following the manufacturer's recommendation. The ligation of the inserts into the pLEXSY vector was performed using T4 DNA ligase (EUROMEDEX) according to the manufacturer's instructions. A total of 80 ng of digested vector and 24 ng of purified insert were used in a final 20 μ L reaction, incubated at 22 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 minutes or overnight at 4 $^{\circ}$ C.

Figure 3. Map of the pLEXSY-hyg2 vector used in this study. The plasmid contains the hyg selection marker, conferring resistance to the drug hygromycin. Image taken from the JENA Bioscience website.

For the construction of pTREX-neo plasmids, the inserts obtained from sub-cloning the pUC57 vector were amplified using primers containing the *Xho*I and *Xba*I restriction enzyme sites, which are present in the pTREX-neo vector. To obtain the constructs APEX2-HA-PTS1-pTREX-neo, APEX2-HA-NLS-pTREX-neo, mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1-pTREX-neo, and mNeonGreen-HA-NLS-pTREX-neo, the pTREX-neo-tomato plasmid was previously digested with *Xho*I and *Xba*I restriction enzymes. The larger band corresponding to pTREX-neo without Tomato, its stuffer sequence, was extracted from the gel, and the cloning was performed using the same protocol described earlier for pLEXSY-hyg. A total of 80 ng of digested vector and 33 ng of purified insert were used in a final 20 μ L reaction, incubated at 22 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 minutes or overnight at 4 $^{\circ}$ C.

Figure 4. Map of the pTREX-neo vector used in this study. The plasmid contains the neo selection marker, conferring resistance to the drug neomycin. Image generated by SnapGene software.

3. Bacterial transformation

After ligation, competent *Escherichia coli* NovaBlue bacteria were transformed through a thermal shock at 42 °C for 30 seconds with 2.5 µL of the aforementioned ligations, followed by a 2-minute incubation on ice. Subsequently, the bacteria were grown in a biological incubator in Luria-Bertani (LB) medium at 37 °C with constant agitation for 1 hour. Later, the bacteria were plated on LB agar medium containing 100 µg/mL of carbenicillin. The plates were then incubated overnight at 37 °C in a biological incubator.

The following day, five colonies from each construct were selected for confirmation of cloning through colony PCR. Briefly, a small fraction of each selected colony was added to a microtube containing Thermo Scientific PCR Master Mix and primers flanking the insert or the plasmid at a concentration of 1 µM. The PCR reaction was programmed as follows: an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 5 minutes, followed by 35 cycles of 95 °C for 30 seconds, 68 °C for 30 seconds for primer annealing, and 72 °C for extension of PCR products, and finally, 72 °C for 7 minutes for final extension. For analysis of positive clones, 2 µL of each PCR reaction was loaded onto a 1% (w/v) agarose gel.

A positive colony from each construct was inoculated into 20 mL of LB medium containing 100 µg/mL of carbenicillin and grown at 37 °C for 16 hours with constant agitation at 200 rpm.

4. Plasmid preparation

DNA plasmid extraction from the cultured positive colonies was performed using the QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit from QIAGEN. Briefly, 5 mL of bacterial culture was centrifuged at 7,000 g for 10 minutes at room temperature. After centrifugation, the bacterial

pellet was resuspended in 250 μ L of Buffer P1 and transferred to a microcentrifuge tube. Subsequently, 250 μ L of Buffer P2 was added and thoroughly mixed by inverting the tube 6 times until the solution became clear. Following this reaction, 350 μ L of Buffer N3 was added, and the solution was mixed by inversion. The tube was then centrifuged for 10 minutes at 17,900 g at room temperature. The supernatant from the previous step was applied to the QIAprep spin column by decantation and centrifuged for 60 seconds. The flow-through was discarded, and the column was washed twice. The first wash was performed with 0.5 mL of Buffer PB, and the second wash with 0.75 mL of Buffer PE. Finally, the columns were placed over a 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube, and the DNA was eluted with 50 μ L of Buffer EB (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.5). The minipreparations were digested with *Bgl*II and *Not*I (for the pLEXSY-neo constructs) or with *Xba*I and *Xho*I (for the pTREX-neo constructs) for a second confirmation of cloning.

The sequences were also confirmed by sequencing conducted by Eurofins Genomics.

5. *L. infantum* transfection

All plasmid constructs were used for episomal transfection, without the need for plasmid digestion for genomic integration. Immediately before transfection, 8 μ g of DNA from each plasmid construct was heat-shocked at 65 $^{\circ}$ C in a dry bath for 30 minutes.

The Human T Cell NucleofactorTM Kit from Lonza was used for transfection. Briefly, 1×10^7 exponential-phase promastigote forms of *L. infantum* were used for each condition. Parasites were centrifuged at 2,000 g for 1 minute, and the pellet was resuspended in 82 μ L of NucleofactorTM Solution for Human T Cells 1, 18 μ L of Supplement 1 solution, and 10 μ L of plasmid (equivalent to 8 μ g). The contents of the microtube were transferred to a specific aluminum cuvette provided by the kit, which was subsequently subjected to a pulse through the electroporation system (program U-033). After the pulse, the parasites were transferred to 10 mL of Schneider medium supplemented with 20% fetal bovine serum and incubated at 27 $^{\circ}$ C for 24 hours. The parasites were then selected with 100 μ g/mL hygromycin B (Sigma Aldrich). After the death of the negative control (transfected with buffers only, without plasmid), approximately two weeks later, the transfected parasites were cloned by serial dilution into 96-well plates. Two clones of each construct were recovered, maintained under antibiotic pressure, and subjected to further analysis. Figure 5 presents the transfection protocol used.

Figure 5. *Leishmania infantum* transfection protocol.

6. APEX2-based protein biotinylation assay

For each condition, 1×10^8 transfected parasites were used. The cultures of parasites were centrifuged at 2,000 g for 5 minutes and resuspended in 5 mL of Schneider medium, followed by the addition of the APEX2 substrate, biotin-phenol (Sigma Aldrich), at 5 mM, and incubated for 1 h at 27 °C in a biological incubator. Subsequently, the oxidizing/catalytic agent of the reaction, H_2O_2 (Sigma Aldrich), was added at 1 mM to enable biotinylation of the organelle proteins. To halt the biotinylation reaction, the cells were washed twice with a quencher solution (10 mM sodium azide, 10 mM sodium ascorbate, and 5 mM Trolox) in PBS. Two conditions were used to analyze the expression of APEX2-HA and the potential biotinylation of cellular compartments: absence of biotin-phenol/presence of H_2O_2 (BP-/ H_2O_2 +); and presence of biotin-phenol/presence of H_2O_2 (BP+/ H_2O_2 +).

After the biotinylation reaction, a fraction of the transfected parasites was prepared for protein analysis by Western blot and streptavidin-blot essays, while another fraction was used for immunofluorescence assays. Figure 6 illustrates the protocol used for the biotinylation assay.

Figure 6. Biotinylation assay protocol.

7. Western-blot and streptavidin-blot

For confirmation of the expression of epissomal mutants and biotinylation of organelle proteins, the parasites were resuspended in radioimmunoprecipitation assay (RIPA) lysis buffer [50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.0, 150 mM NaCl, 0.1% (w/v) SDS, 0.5% (w/v) sodium deoxycholate, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, 1 tablet of protease inhibitor (cOmpleteTM, EDTA-free protease inhibitor cocktail, Roche), 10 mM sodium azide, 10 mM sodium ascorbate, and 5 mM Trolox] immediately after the biotinylation assay, at a ratio of 4 volumes of RIPA solution to 1 volume of parasite pellet. The samples were vortexed, incubated on ice for 5 minutes, and centrifuged at 12,000 g for 10 minutes at 4 °C. The supernatants were transferred to new microtubes. The protein extracts were analyzed by SDS-PAGE, transferred to nitrocellulose membranes, and stained with 0.1% (w/v) Ponceau S in 5% (v/v) acetic acid.

After transfer, the membranes were blocked with 3% BSA in PBS. For analysis of APEX2 protein expression, the α -HA Tag Monoclonal antibody conjugated with HRP (horseradish peroxidase) (InvitrogenTM, reference: 2-2.2.14) was used at a dilution of 1:7500. For detection of biotinylated organelle proteins, streptavidin-HRP (Merck Millipore, reference: 18-152) was used at a dilution of 1:30000. After appropriate incubations, all nitrocellulose membranes were incubated for 1 minute with ECL substrates (Bio-Rad) and/or Clarity Max

ECL Substrates (Bio-Rad) and exposed on the chemiluminescence and colorimetric filter of the ChemiDoc instrument (Bio-Rad) to obtain images.

8. Immunofluorescence assays

In addition to validating the expression of APEX2-HA-NLS and APEX2-HA-PTS1, the parasites were subjected to fluorescence microscopy analysis to confirm the correct targeting of proteins to the organelles of interest (nucleus or glycosome). The same immunofluorescence assay was used to analyze the biotinylated proteins after the biotinylation assay. The preparation of parasites for immunofluorescence was carried out as follows: initially, the parasites were suspended in 3.7% formaldehyde in PBS. Then, they were centrifuged at 500 g for 4 minutes, suspended in 0.1% Triton X-100, and incubated on ice for 10 minutes. Subsequently, 0.1 M glycine was added and incubated again for 10 minutes on ice. A total of 2×10^6 total parasites were used per well on each mounting slide. Blocking of the slides was performed with 5% milk in PBS with the addition of 0.05% NP-40. For image contrast of properly labeled and analyzed compartments in *L. infantum*, the primary antibody α -HA Monoclonal (Invitrogen, reference: 26183) was used at a dilution of 1:3,000, and the secondary antibody GAM IgG (H+L) AF488 (ThermoFisher) at a dilution of 1:300. Streptavidin conjugated to FITC was used at a dilution of 1:100 for detecting biotinylated proteins. After appropriate incubations, the slides were washed three times with PBS. DAPI (ThermoFisher, reference: 62248) was used at 2 μ g/mL for nuclear staining. The use of anti-fading ProLong™ Diamond Antifade Mountant (Invitrogen) was also employed.

III. Results

1. Cloning of the APEX2 and mNeonGreen genes into the pLEXSY-hyg2 and pTREX-neo vectors

The pLEXSY-hyg2 vector, chosen for expression in *L. infantum*, and the pTREX-neo vector, for expression in *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei*, were digested for subsequent ligation with the APEX2-HA-NLS, APEX2-HA-PTS1, mNeonGreen-HA-NLS, and mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1 fragments. The pLEXSY-hyg2 plasmid was digested with the *Bgl*III and *Not*I restriction enzymes, releasing a 1,107 bp sequence (stuffer 1) and the linearized vector of 8,026 bp (Figure 7). The original pTREX-neo-tomato plasmid was digested with the *Xho*I and *Xba*I restriction enzymes, releasing a 1,464 bp sequence (stuffer - tomato) and the linearized vector (6,206 bp) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Digestion of pLEXSY-hyg2 and pTREX-neo vectors for cloning. 5 μ g of pLEXSY-hyg2 were incubated with *Bgl*III and *Not*I. Double digestion releasing pLEXSY-hyg2 (8,026 bp) and a stuffer (1,107 bp). 5 μ g of pTREX-neo were incubated with *Xho*I and *Xba*I. Double digestion releasing pTREX-neo (6,206 bp) and a stuffer (1,464 bp). Digestion reaction results were observed on a 1% (w/v) agarose gel. Ladder, 1 Kb DNA ladder marker.

After the amplification fragments were ligated to their respective linearized plasmids, the vectors were used for the transformation of Novablue *E. coli* K12 strain (Novagen) and selected with 100 μ g/mL carbenicillin. For confirmation of cloning into the pLEXSY-hyg vector, several colonies were subjected to PCR to amplify the gene of interest. Out of 5 colonies tested for each construct, we obtained 5 positive colonies for APEX2-HA-PTS1-pLEXSY-hyg2, APEX2-HA-NLS-pLEXSY-hyg2, and mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1-pLEXSY-hyg2, and 4 positive colonies for mNeonGreen-HA-NLS-pLEXSY-hyg2 (Figure 8A-B). For a second confirmation of cloning, plasmid minipreps were extracted from 1 colony of each construct and subjected to restriction analysis. The *Bgl*III and *Not*I enzymes were used again (Figure 8C), releasing the linearized vector (approximately 8,000 bp) and a sequence of approximately 900 bp (corresponding to the inserts). Sequencing analysis confirmed that the products were successfully cloned into the vector.

Figure 8. Confirmation of insert cloning into the pLEXSY-hyg2 vector. A-B, Amplification of APEX-HA-PTS1, APEX2-HA-NLS, mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1, and mNeonGreen-HA-NLS genes through PCR from colonies of *E. coli* Novablue transfected with vector/insert ligation and selected with 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ carbenicillin. A portion of each colony was subjected to PCR using specific primers for each gene of interest. C, Electrophoresis analysis of the pLEXSY-hyg2-insert plasmid (1- APEX-HA-PTS1; 2- APEX2-HA-NLS; 3- mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1; 4- mNeonGreen-HA-NLS) digested with *Bgl*III and *Not*I. Ladder, 1 Kb DNA ladder marker.

Similarly, for confirmation of insert cloning into the pTREX-neo vector, several colonies were subjected to colony PCR to amplify the gene of interest. Out of 5 colonies tested for the APEX2-HA-PTS1-pTREX-neo and mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1-pTREX-neo constructs, we obtained 4 positive colonies for the first construct and 2 positive colonies for the second construct. Out of 4 colonies tested for the APEX2-HA-NLS-pTREX-neo construct, we obtained 2 positive colonies. Finally, out of 2 colonies tested for the mNeonGreen-HA-NLS-pTREX-neo construct, we obtained 2 positive colonies (Figure 9A). For a second confirmation of

cloning, plasmid minipreps were extracted from 1 colony of each construct and subjected to restriction analysis. The *XhoI* and *XbaI* enzymes were used (Figure 9B), releasing the linearized vector (approximately 6,200 bp) and a sequence of approximately 900 bp (corresponding to the inserts). Sequencing analysis also revealed that the products were successfully cloned into the vector.

Figure 9. Confirmation of insert cloning into the pTREX-neo vector. A, Amplification of APEX2-PTS1-HA, APEX2-NLS-HA, mNeonGreen-PTS1-HA, and mNeonGreen-NLS-HA genes through PCR from colonies of *E. coli* Novablue transfected with vector/insert ligation and selected with 100 μ g/mL carbenicillin. A portion of each colony was subjected to PCR using specific primers for each gene of interest. B, Electrophoresis analysis of the pTREX-neo-insert plasmid (1- APEX-HA-PTS1; 2- APEX2-HA-NLS; 3- mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1; 4- mNeonGreen-HA-NLS) digested with *XhoI* and *XbaI*. L, 1 Kb DNA ladder marker.

2. Cell culture of *L. infantum*

For the maintenance of the *in vitro* culture of the parasite, the culture medium of *L. infantum* promastigote forms was changed every two days, after they reached the exponential phase, as shown in Figure 10. It was also during this phase that the parasites were separated for transfection.

Figure 10. Promastigote forms of *L. infantum* after 48 hours of culture medium change. The image was captured using an inverted phase contrast microscope.

3. Confirmation of protein expression by Western blot

As previously explained, the cassettes contain the APEX2 or mNeonGreen genes fused to a sequence of codons for three hemagglutinins, along with the signal peptide. Consequently, following transfection, Western blot analyses were performed to detect the presence of the proteins fused to the peptides through labeling with the α -HA antibody.

The transfected cultures were cloned through serial dilution in 96-well plates, and 2 clones from each construct were recovered and expanded. According to Figure 11, it can be observed that the APEX2-HA-PTS1 and APEX2-HA-NLS proteins (35 kDa) are well expressed in the protein extract of the parasites transfected with the cassette, although the expression of the APEX2-HA-NLS protein was lower for clone F10 of the APEX2-HA-NLS construct (Figure 11A). Proteins with the mNeonGreen insert showed low expression in the analyzed protein extract, except for the clone H7 of mNeonGreen-HA-NLS, which showed no expression (Figure 11B). Considering that, for this Western blot analysis involving the mNeonGreen protein, using the same exposure interval available for the APEX2 proteins and the same substrate for detection (ECL substrates, Bio-rad), there was no detection of the α -HA antibody on the membrane. In fact, Image B refers to the membrane after incubation with Clarity Max ECL substrate (BioRad), subjected to a longer exposure period to obtain this result. There was no α -HA antibody labeling in the wild-type parasite extract (WT).

Figure 11. Detection of APEX2 and mNeonGreen proteins by Western blot. A, Extracts of cloned parasites APEX2-HA-PTS1 (F9 and G8), APEX2-HA-NLS (F10 and G9); B, Extracts of cloned parasites mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1 (F8 and G7) and mNeonGreen-HA-NLS (G8 and H7), and wild-type parasites (WT) were probed with α -HA antibodies (1:4,000). A band corresponding to approximately 35 kDa is observed for the proteins.

4. Confirmation of organelle protein biotinylation

To assess the efficacy of the APEX2-based biotinylation assay in inducing post-translational chemical modification in proteins present in the glycosome or nucleus of *L. infantum*, two conditions, with or without biotin-phenol substrate (BP), were applied to the transgenic parasites: (i) BP+ / H₂O₂+, (ii) BP- / H₂O₂+. Due to a delay in the delivery of higher purity hydrogen peroxide reagent from Sigma Aldrich, we initially decided to use a lower-grade hydrogen peroxide obtained from a pharmacy while awaiting the arrival of the original reagent (results attached). Following the biotinylation assay, soluble parasite proteins were obtained by RIPA treatment and separated by SDS-PAGE. A streptavidin-HRP blot analysis was performed to probe for biotinylated proteins under the tested conditions. The results below refer to the experiment using Sigma's H₂O₂.

Figure 12. Confirmation of the biotinylation assay by streptavidin blot. A, Extracts of G8 and F9 cloned parasites APEX-HA-PTS1 and negative control (parasites transfected with the empty plasmid without the APEX2 sequence) after biotinylation assay using 1mM higher purity and higher concentrated hydrogen peroxide (Hydrogen peroxide 30%, Sigma Aldrich) and resuspended in RIPA buffer. B, Extract of F10 and G9 cloned parasites APEX-HA-NLS.

According to Figure 12, several bands were detected in all the conditions, including the two lanes of the negative control - parasites transfected with the empty plasmid corresponding to the presence of potentially naturally biotinylated proteins or intrinsic background of the methodology. However, considering that the same quantity of parasites was subjected to the biotinylation assay and the same amount of protein from each sample was applied to the gel, a higher detection of biotinylated proteins was detected in the presence of biotin and hydrogen peroxide in all the APEX2 clones, indicating the potential success of the reaction. Among the APEX2-HA-PTS mutants, clones F9 and G8 showed an equivalent expression of the APEX2 (Figure 11A), however clone F9 presented a stronger protein biotinylation signal (Figure 12A). Regarding the APEX2-HA-NLS clones, clone G9 appears to be more active in expressing the APEX2 protein than clone F10 (Figure 11A), and more efficient to biotinylate proteins (Figure 12B).

5. Immunofluorescence image analysis

In order to validate the targeting of proteins to their respective organelles through the fused signal peptide, mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1 and mNeonGreen-HA-NLS mutants were created. We made multiple attempts to observe the expression of fluorescent proteins in the target organelles, conducting fluorescence microscope analyses at intervals of 48 hours, 4 days, 7 days, and even 2 weeks after transfection. Fluorescence was detected through fluorescence microscopy in few cases after cell fixation on the glass slide, but, regrettably, the fluorescent signal was ephemera, without time to take a picture, that could be a problem of quick photobleaching.

Regarding the APEX-HA-PTS1 and APEX-HA-NLS mutants, we also employed fluorescence microscopy to assess their correct targeting to the glycosomes and nucleus, respectively. Through immunofluorescence assays using the monoclonal α -HA antibody, along with a secondary antibody GAM IgG AF488, we were able to confirm the precise targeting of both proteins (Figure 13). APEX-HA-PTS1 protein (clone G8, Figure 13) clearly localized only in punctuate structures within the parasite cytoplasm, suggesting that it might be localized within glycosome. APEX-HA-NLS protein (clone G9, Figure 13) displayed a diffused signal but with a stronger signal in the middle of the core of the cell, suggestion that might be localized closed to the nucleus and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) region of the unicellular parasite. However, our attempts to perform nuclear labeling using DAPI were not successful (not shown) and we cannot affirm that the protein localized within the nucleus/ER.

Figure 13. Immunofluorescence of APEX2-HA-PTS1 and APEX-HA-NLS proteins. Immunofluorescence was performed using α -HA antibodies (1:3,000) and goat anti-mouse IgG antibodies conjugated with Alexa Fluor 488 (1:300). The image was analysed using QuPath software.

After the biotinylation assay, we proceeded with immunofluorescence analysis using streptavidin-FITC of the mutants expressing APEX-HA-PTS1 and APEX-HA-NLS under two conditions: BP-/H₂O₂+ and BP+/H₂O₂+. In order to revealed biotinylated proteins, after several optimization of APEX2-based biotinylation assay, we were able to observe a stained punctate structures within the parasite cytoplasm, suggesting that the proteins neighboring APEX-HA-PTS1 might be localized within glycosome (Figure 14). However, despite our efforts, we were unable to observe any staining using the streptavidin probe, resulting in a lack of labeling in APEX-HA-NLS mutants (image not shown).

Figure 14. Immunofluorescence of the biotinylated proteins neighbouring APEX2-HA-PTS1 protein. Immunofluorescence was performed with streptavidin conjugated to FITC (1:100). Genomic DNA and kinetoplast (blue) are labelled with DAPI.

The results presented above are preliminary, and to ensure data consistency, we plan to repeat the immunofluorescence experiments using new reagents such as DAPI and streptavidin, with different concentrations.

IV. Discussion

The proteins and enzymes present in the glycosomes of trypanosomatids have been explored as significant targets for the development of new drugs. Despite being recognized for housing the majority of enzymes in the glycolytic pathway, additional pathways considered essential for the survival and nutrition of the parasites have been specifically identified within the glycosomes: succinic fermentation, the oxidative branch of the pentose phosphate pathway, purine salvage, pyrimidine biosynthesis, and sugar nucleotide biosynthesis (Allmann *et al.*, 2006). In parallel, despite the conservation of the protein import process into the glycosome matrix, notable variations have been reported among organisms from different phylogenetic groups (Galland *et al.*, 2010). Specifically concerning parasitic trypanosomatids, these variations provide promising opportunities in the search for new drugs, as well as enabling comparative studies on the evolutionary adaptation of these species.

Given the fundamental importance and the multiple functions performed by glycosomes in trypanosomatids, significant efforts have been dedicated to study the protein composition of this organelle. Early studies used the technique of density gradient centrifugation enrichment prior to proteomic analyses (Jamdhade *et al.*, 2015; Acosta *et al.*, 2019; Colasante *et al.*, 2006). While this approach is useful for defining the protein environment of a subcellular compartment, it can become complex depending on the quality of the purified fraction and may not cover subdomains that are not part of a specific structure that has been purified. To overcome this limitation, proximity labeling approaches have been increasingly employed. Vélez-Ramírez *et al.*, in 2021, introduced an innovation by employing, for the first time in a eukaryotic human pathogen, the APEX2 proximity labeling technique to identify the adjacent proteome of flagellar proteins. In this study, the authors described 346 novel proteins within the flagellar proteome that had not been previously identified in earlier studies, highlighting the

success of the technique. To date, no studies applying APEX2 to *L. infantum*, *T. rangeli*, and *T. cruzi* have been found.

The initial objective of this project was to validate and apply the APEX2 methodology for the analysis of specific intracellular compartments, glycosomes and the nucleus in *L. infantum*, *T. rangeli*, and *T. brucei*, organelles that had not been explored using this approach in these species. We also intended to conduct the first comparative proteomic analyses among these species. However, due to the ambitious scope of the project in relation to the limited time for conducting all experiments, as well as unforeseen delays in the arrival of reagents and protocol adaptation, it was not possible to fully achieve all the established objectives. Thus, this stage, within the broader scope of the comparative proteomic project among the three parasites, focused on the application of the APEX2 technology for investigating proteins in the glycosomes and nucleus of *L. infantum*, as well as constructing plasmids for subsequent transfection into *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei*.

To start the cassette construction containing APEX2 and mNeonGreen, the pLEXSY-hyg vector (Figure 3) was chosen for episomal expression in *L. infantum*. The expression vector pTREX-neo (Figure 4) was used for the construction of cassettes that will be employed for transfection into *T. rangeli* and *T. brucei* in the future. Images 7, 8, and 9 show the process of molecular cloning and confirm the insertion of the inserts into the expected vectors. After transfection into *L. infantum*, parasites containing the cassettes were then assessed for protein expression through western blot and immunofluorescence. The western blot of cloned parasite extracts clearly demonstrates the expression of APEX2-HA and the specificity of the α -HA antibody, as there is no cross-reactivity with any protein in the *L. infantum* extract, given that the band at approximately 35 kDa is absent in wild-type parasites. For the cloned parasites with mNeonGreen, protein expression was relatively low. Even with the use of the ClarityMax ECL solution for blot detection and an extended image exposure time, we did not achieve the same intensity observed in the APEX2 clones. The low protein expression of mNeonGreen, while not fully understood, could explain the very low or even the lack of fluorescence in observations of these clones using fluorescence microscopy. Through fluorescence microscopy, we confirmed the correct targeting of APEX2 proteins to the glycosomes (PTS1) or to the nucleus (NLS). In Figure 13, for the APEX2-HA-PTS1 clone, numerous punctate vesicles corresponding to glycosomes are observable, contrasting with the pattern observed for the APEX-HA-NLS mutant, where the protein is distributed diffusely but strongly in the nuclear/ER region.

Due to a delay in the delivery of high-purity hydrogen peroxide reagent (Sigma Aldrich), we decided to proceed with the biotinylation assays using lower-quality hydrogen peroxide obtained from a pharmacy. This decision was made due to the lack of available alternatives and with the aim of avoiding schedule delays. Two concentrations of this hydrogen peroxide were evaluated: 1 mM and 5 mM, along with various concentrations of streptavidin-HRP, in an effort to mitigate potential false-positive results. Supplementary Figure 1 displays the outcome of the biotinylation assay for the NLS F10 clone, utilizing a concentration of 1 mM hydrogen peroxide. The result indicates the lack of specificity of the ThermoFisher streptavidin-HRP at the used dilution (1:4,000), as well as the lack of success in the experiment. This is evident because even in the absence of antibody specificity, the condition with biotin and H₂O₂ should theoretically demonstrate higher expression of the theoretically biotinylated proteins. Subsequently, a new biotinylation test was conducted on the APEX2-HA-PTS1 clones (Supplementary Figure 2). This time, a concentration of 5 mM hydrogen peroxide and a 1:10,000 dilution of streptavidin-HRP were used in an attempt to minimize false-positive results from the previous experiment. The results revealed a slight difference between the controls and the tests of the transfected clones. However, the similarity in results between the negative control (parasites transfected with the empty plasmid) and the tests on the clones limited the

conclusiveness of the assay, rendering it inconclusive once again. With the acquisition of new reagents, Sigma's hydrogen peroxide and a new Invitrogen™ Streptavidin-HRP, we proceeded to re-run the experiments (Figure 12), allowing for the validation of the biotinylation assay in all clones. Based on these results, we concluded that the hydrogen peroxide obtained from the pharmacy possibly contained components and/or stabilizers that interacted with one or more of the reagents used in the biotinylation assay, thereby impairing proper APEX2-based protein biotinylation that depend of oxidation condition.

While there was a noticeable enhancement in the labeling of biotinylated proteins in the BP+/H₂O₂+ (Sigma) condition across all analysed clones (Figure 12), the presence of biotinylated proteins in the negative control groups (BP-/H₂O₂+ and parasites transfected with the empty plasmid) was unexpected. This is because in previous studies utilizing APEX2, the number of biotinylated proteins in the negative control was often considerably lower than in the assay conditions (Rim *et al.*, 2023; Tran *et al.*, 2021). In this context, we were questioning the natural frequency of protein biotinylation in *L. infantum*. Most organisms have enzyme for attachment of biotin to other proteins. The biotin ligase protein plays a role in selectively adding biotin to a specific lysine in the active site of newly synthesized enzymes (Chapman-Smith *et al.*, 1999). In *Leishmania*, three mitochondrial enzymes, acetyl-CoA carboxylase, 3-methylcrotonyl-CoA carboxylase, and propionyl-CoA carboxylase, rely on this biotinylation for their activity (Rajak *et al.*, 2021). Acetyl-CoA carboxylase (241 kDa) is a heterohexamer of biotin carboxyl carrier protein (17 kDa), biotin carboxylase (55 kDa), and two non-identical carboxyl transferase subunits (alpha and beta), with molecular weights not provided. 3-methylcrotonyl-CoA carboxylase consists of an alpha subunit (75 kDa) and a beta subunit (62 kDa) assembled into an $\alpha\beta_6$ dodecamer. Propionyl CoA carboxylase is a large enzyme (~770 kDa) composed of 6 alpha subunits (73 kDa) and 6 beta subunits (53 kDa) (information retrieved from the Protein Data Bank Japan bioinformatics database). However, while the presence of these naturally biotinylated proteins may explain part of the proteins detected in the negative controls of Figure 12, this explanation would not encompass all the observed proteins. Therefore, it is likely that these detected proteins may be naturally biotinylated proteins specific to *L. infantum* or may be subject to non-specific streptavidin labeling. New assays will be necessary to confirm the presence or absence of false positives and to clarify this issue more accurately.

While APEX2 has not yet been used in proteomic mapping studies of glycosomes in trypanosomatids, several other studies have focused on the characterization of these proteins. In *L. infantum*, although a specific study to determine the glycosomal proteome through organelle fractionation has not been conducted, Sanchiz and colleagues (2020) conducted a study using total protein extracts from promastigote forms, resulting in the identification of various proteins. Besides peroxins (PEX 5 and PEX 6/7), proteins related to peroxisome biogenesis, as well as enzymes of glycolysis and gluconeogenesis pathways, enzymes involved in the purine salvage pathway, and most enzymes involved in de novo pyrimidine synthesis were identified (Sanchiz *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, a comprehensive proteomic analysis of glycosomes in *L. donovani*, enriched through density gradient fractionation of the glycosomal fraction, led to the identification of more proteins, involved in the pentose phosphate, lipid metabolism, and purine and pyrimidine metabolism pathways (Jamdhade *et al.*, 2015). For the characterization of the glycosomal proteome of the procyclic stage of *T. brucei*, the most comprehensive study was conducted using epitope tagging, magnetic bead enrichment, and quantitative SILAC proteomics (Güther *et al.*, 2014). In addition to the proteins discussed earlier, the researchers also identified members of protein phosphatase families. They discuss the possible connection of these phosphatases with relevant information for the cell cycle or metabolic state, which may be transmitted from the cytosol to the glycosomes. These enzymes would play a fundamental role in metabolic control through dephosphorylation of the

received signals (Güther *et al.*, 2014). Despite these findings, the researchers of the aforementioned articles acknowledge the limitations of the glycosome enrichment approach, as identification is compromised by inevitable contamination from other compartments, especially the mitochondria. Proteomic studies of glycosomes in *T. rangeli* were not carried out in our knowledge. Although there are similarities in the identified proteins from proteomic mapping studies of glycosomes in trypanosomatids, comparing and discussing the identified proteins is challenging due to the diversity of methodologies adopted in the articles, which lack a standardized approach. Therefore, a proteomic study using the same approach across different types of trypanosomatids could provide valuable insights for a discussion on the metabolic adaptation of this group.

In conclusion, this study has established that APEX2 proximity labeling can be implemented within the biochemical environment of *L. infantum*, although further assays are required to confirm the natural biotinylation of certain proteins in this microorganism. As a perspective, we aim to repeat the immunofluorescence assays to obtain undeniable pictures of protein biotinylation in target organelles using new reagents. Regarding the constructs containing the mNeonGreen sequence that were produced as control of transfection and of transit to glycosome and nucleus using signal peptide, if fluorescence is not observed in subsequent attempts, new alternatives may be considered and implemented, such as using a different fluorescent protein or a molecular marker specific to target organelles. Concerning the plasmids pTREX-neo-APEX2-HA-PTS1/NLS and pTREX-neo-mNeonGreen-HA-PTS1/NLS, which were designed for expression in *T. brucei* and *T. rangeli*, they are scheduled for transfection in the coming months. These activities will take place at the Laboratory of Biochemistry and Protein Chemistry at the University of Brasília, Brazil, where future proteomic analyses of *L. infantum* are also planned. By combining the proteomic datasets obtained from these three species, our aim is to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of glycosomes and nucleus. This approach has the potential to provide valuable insights into the metabolic adaptation of this group. Furthermore, our research may identify potential pharmaceutical targets for the treatment of diseases related to trypanosomatids.

Acknowledgements

I would like to take this opportunity to express my deepest gratitude to everyone who played a crucial role in making this second year of my master's degree a reality. During an enriching year in France, I had the chance to immerse myself in a learning and research environment that profoundly shaped my understanding and perspective both personally and academically. What once seemed distant now sparks my curiosity to explore and strengthens my confidence.

First and foremost, I extend my thanks to the IBEEES-INBOUND program committee, and the Master 2 Biodiversité, Écologie et Évolution, Parcours MES who made this unique experience possible. I appreciate the intensive French course offered by the MNHN at the beginning of the semester and the financial support throughout the exchange, which were instrumental in my integration and academic success in France. To my supervisors, Sebastien Charneau and Izabela Bastos, I am grateful for your exceptional guidance. From the bureaucratic procedures in Brazil to the complexities of my internship in the laboratory, your support has been indispensable. I also express my appreciation to the coordinator of my internship, Pr. Philippe Grellier, whose dedication and leadership were essential, as well as Pr. Coralie Martin. I Thank Dr. Frédéric Fercoq for microscopy imaging.

Finally, I want to thank all the professors from whom I had the opportunity to learn. Your patience in explanations, constant support in English, and patience to clear my doubts were crucial to my progress and success in the courses. To my laboratory colleagues, who shared laughter, challenges, and discoveries, my gratitude is enormous. You made the work environment not only productive but also enjoyable and light-hearted.

Bibliography

1. Acosta H, Burchmore R, Naula C, Gualdrón-López M, Quintero-Troconis E, Cáceres AJ, Michels PAM, Concepción JL, Quiñones W. Proteomic analysis of glycosomes from *Trypanosoma cruzi* epimastigotes. *Mol Biochem Parasitol.* 2019 Apr;229:62-74. doi: 10.1016/j.molbiopara.2019.02.008
2. Allmann S, Bringaud F. Glycosomes: A comprehensive view of their metabolic roles in *T. brucei*. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol.* 2017 Apr;85:85-90. doi: 10.1016/j.biocel.2017.01.015
3. Barros-Alvarez X, Gualdrón-López M, Acosta H, Cáceres AJ, Graminha MA, Michels PA, Concepción JL, Quiñones W. Glycosomal targets for anti-trypanosomatid drug discovery. *Curr Med Chem.* 2014;21(15):1679-706. doi: 10.2174/09298673113209990139
4. Chapman-Smith A, Cronan JE Jr. The enzymatic biotinylation of proteins: a post-translational modification of exceptional specificity. *Trends Biochem Sci.* 1999 Sep;24(9):359-63. doi: 10.1016/s0968-0004(99)01438-3
5. Choi-Rhee E, Schulman H, Cronan JE. Promiscuous protein biotinylation by *Escherichia coli* biotin protein ligase. *Protein Sci.* 2004 Nov;13(11):3043-50. doi: 10.1110/ps.04911804
6. Colasante C, Ellis M, Ruppert T, Voncken F. Comparative proteomics of glycosomes from bloodstream form and procyclic culture form *Trypanosoma brucei brucei*. *Proteomics.* 2006 Jun;6(11):3275-93. doi: 10.1002/pmic.200500668
7. Galland N, Michels PA. Comparison of the peroxisomal matrix protein import system of different organisms. Exploration of possibilities for developing inhibitors of the import system of trypanosomatids for anti-parasite chemotherapy. *Eur J Cell Biol.* 2010 Sep; 89(9):621-37. doi: 10.1016/j.ejcb.2010.04.001
8. Grisard EC, Stoco PH, Wagner G, Sincero TC, Rotava G, Rodrigues JB, Snoeijer CQ, Koerich LB, Sperandio MM, Bayer-Santos E, Fragoso SP, Goldenberg S, Triana O, Vallejo GA, Tyler KM, Dávila AM, Steindel M. Transcriptomic analyses of the avirulent protozoan parasite *Trypanosoma rangeli*. *Mol Biochem Parasitol.* 2010 Nov; 174(1):18-25.
9. Guhl F, Vallejo GA. *Trypanosoma (Herpetosoma) rangeli* Tejera, 1920: an updated review. *SciELO Brazil.* 2003 June. DOI: 10.1590/s0074-02762003000400001
10. Güther ML, Urbaniak MD, Tavendale A, Prescott A, Ferguson MA. High-confidence glycosome proteome for procyclic form *Trypanosoma brucei* by epitope-tag organelle enrichment and SILAC proteomics. *J Proteome Res.* 2014 Jun 6;13(6):2796-806. doi: 10.1021/pr401209w
11. Huang MS, Lin WC, Chang JH, Cheng CH, Wang HY, Mou KY. The cysteine-free single mutant C32S of APEX2 is a highly expressed and active fusion tag for proximity labeling applications. *Protein Sci.* 2019 Sep;28(9):1703-1712. doi: 10.1002/pro.3685
12. Jamdhade MD, Pawar H, Chavan S, Sathe G, Umasankar PK, Mahale KN, Dixit T, Madugundu AK, Prasad TS, Gowda H, Pandey A, Patole MS. Comprehensive proteomics analysis of glycosomes from *Leishmania donovani*. *OMICS.* 2015 Mar; 19(3):157-70. doi: 10.1089/omi.2014.0163
13. Jardim A, Hardie DB, Boitz J, Borchers CH. Proteomic Profiling of *Leishmania donovani* Promastigote Subcellular Organelles. *J Proteome Res.* 2018 Mar 2;17(3):1194-1215. doi: 10.1021/acs.jproteome.7b00817
14. Lam SS, Martell JD, Kamer KJ, Deerinck TJ, Ellisman MH, Mootha VK, Ting AY. Directed evolution of APEX2 for electron microscopy and proximity labeling. *Nat Methods.* 2015 Jan;12(1):51-4. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.3179
15. Marlière NP, Lorenzo MG, Guarneri AA. *Trypanosoma rangeli* infection increases the exposure and predation endured by *Rhodnius prolixus*. *Parasitology.* 2022 Feb;149(2):155-160. doi: 10.1017/S0031182021001682
16. Martell JD, Deerinck TJ, Sancak Y, Poulos TL, Mootha VK, Sosinsky GE, Ellisman MH, Ting AY. Engineered ascorbate peroxidase as a genetically encoded reporter for electron microscopy. *Nat Biotechnol.* 2012 Nov;30(11):1143-8. doi: 10.1038/nbt.2375
17. Moyersoen J, Choe J, Fan E, Hol WG, Michels PA. Biogenesis of peroxisomes and glycosomes: trypanosomatid glycosome assembly is a promising new drug target. *FEMS Microbiol Rev.* 2004 Nov; 28(5):603-43. doi: 10.1016/j.femsre.2004.06.004
18. Opperdoes FR, Szikora JP. In silico prediction of the glycosomal enzymes of *Leishmania major* and trypanosomes. *Mol Biochem Parasitol.* 2006 Jun;147(2):193-206. doi: 10.1016/j.molbiopara.2006.02.010
19. Rajak MK, Bhatnagar S, Pandey S, Kumar S, Verma S, Patel AK, Sundd M. *Leishmania major* biotin protein ligase forms a unique cross-handshake dimer. *Acta Crystallogr D Struct Biol.* 2021 Apr 1;77(Pt 4):510-521. doi: 10.1107/S2059798321001418
20. Rim EY, Nusse R. APEX2-Mediated Proximity Labeling of Wnt Receptor Interactors Upon Pathway Activation. *MicroPubl Biol.* 2023 May 15;2023:10.17912/micropub.biology.000817. doi: 10.17912/micropub.biology.000817

21. Roux KJ, Kim DI, Raida M, Burke B. A promiscuous biotin ligase fusion protein identifies proximal and interacting proteins in mammalian cells. *J Cell Biol.* 2012 Mar 19;196(6):801-10. doi: 10.1083/jcb.201112098
22. Sanchiz Á, Morato E, Rastrojo A, Camacho E, González-de la Fuente SG, Marina A, Aguado B, Requena JM. The Experimental Proteome of *Leishmania infantum* Promastigote and Its Usefulness for Improving Gene Annotations. *Genes (Basel).* 2020 Sep 2;11(9):1036. doi: 10.3390/genes11091036
23. Tran JR, Paulson DI, Moresco JJ, Adam SA, Yates JR, Goldman RD, Zheng Y. An APEX2 proximity ligation method for mapping interactions with the nuclear lamina. *J Cell Biol.* 2021 Jan 4;220(1):e202002129. doi: 10.1083/jcb.202002129
24. Trinkle-Mulcahy L. Recent advances in proximity-based labeling methods for interactome mapping. *F1000Res.* 2019 Jan 31;8:F1000 Faculty Rev-135. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.16903
25. Vélez-Ramírez DE, Shimogawa MM, Ray SS, Lopez A, Rayatpisheh S, Langousis G, Gallagher-Jones M, Dean S, Wohlschlegel JA, Hill KL. APEX2 Proximity Proteomics Resolves Flagellum Subdomains and Identifies Flagellum Tip-Specific Proteins in *Trypanosoma brucei*. *mSphere.* 2021 Feb 10;6(1):e01090-20. doi: 10.1128/mSphere.01090-20
26. Vertommen D, Van Roy J, Szikora JP, Rider MH, Michels PA, Opperdoes FR. Differential expression of glycosomal and mitochondrial proteins in the two major life-cycle stages of *Trypanosoma brucei*. *Mol Biochem Parasitol.* 2008 Apr;158(2):189-201. doi: 10.1016/j.molbiopara.2007.12.008
27. World Health Organization. Leishmaniasis. [Accessed August 2, 2023]. Available online at https://www.who.int/health-topics/leishmaniasis#tab=tab_1
28. World Health Organization. Trypanosomiasis, human African (sleeping sickness). 2023 May. [Accessed August 2, 2023]. Available online at [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/trypanosomiasis-human-african-\(sleeping-sickness\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/trypanosomiasis-human-african-(sleeping-sickness))

Appendices

Supplementary Figure 1. Verification of the biotinylation assay of clone NLS F10 using H₂O₂ purchased from a pharmacy. A, Streptavidin-blot of the APEX2 biotinylation assay of clone APEX2-HA-NLS F10. Four conditions were tested: (i) absence of biotin-phenol/absence of H₂O₂ (BP-/H₂O₂-); (ii) absence of biotin-phenol/presence of H₂O₂ (BP-/H₂O₂+); (iii) presence of biotin-phenol/absence of H₂O₂ (BP+/H₂O₂-); and, (iv) presence of biotin-phenol/presence of H₂O₂ (BP+/H₂O₂+). H₂O₂ was used at 1mM concentration. B, Western-blot with α -HA labelling to verify APEX2-HA-NLS protein expression.

A

(Streptavidin: 1:10000)

B

(Anti-HA-HRP: 1:7500)

Supplementary Figure 2. Verification of the biotinylation assay of PTS clones using low-purity H₂O₂. A, Streptavidin-blot of the APEX2 biotinylation assay of PTS clones F9 and PTS G8. Two conditions were tested: with and without hydrogen peroxide (i) BP+ / H₂O₂+, (ii) BP+ / H₂O₂-. H₂O₂ was used at 5mM concentration. B, Western blot with α -HA labelling to verify APEX2-HA-PTS1 protein expression. The negative control of both images refers to the extract of parasites transfected with the empty pLEXSY-hyg plasmid, without the APEX2 sequence.